

THE PROBLEM OF TEACHING AND LEARNING VOCABULARY

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Annotation: The aim of the course work is to analyze the different ways of teaching and learning vocabulary and find innovative methods which can be effective in the EFL classrooms.

Key words: vocabulary, work, analyze, collection, language, speech activity, learning, objective, reading.

The main objective of the work is to analyze how teaching and learning vocabulary can be organized in an interesting way that can provide opportunities which enable students to use the language structure appropriately when they communicate.

In the theoretical part the most interesting and useful teaching and learning vocabulary techniques have been listed. In this course paper was investigated the process of writing, how to teach it as one of the most difficult and the most important types of speech activity, the ways to overcome the difficulties that students faced by.

Introduction

Vocabulary is a collection of words and phrases in language. Teaching vocabulary to students so that they have a large, expansive word knowledge and then understand the meaning behind the words, enables them to effectively express themselves clearly and in detail. It's equally as important as grammar.

Vocabulary and grammar work together to enhance not only knowledge, but the core language skills of reading, writing, speaking and listening. Knowing and understanding a vast collection of words, where they fit and how they function in sentence structure is vitally important.

Vocabulary is the first and foremost important step in language acquisition. In a classroom the foreign language learning can be made interesting and efficient, interactive and interesting with the introduction of appropriate vocabulary exercises. This paper is an attempt to study and explore the various methodologies that can be incorporated in the teaching of vocabulary items in a language classroom.

Students learn vocabulary directly and indirectly. A student's vocabulary portfolio increases from the age of speaking through the ages of structured learning in a classroom environment. Having active vocabulary lists can increase a student's ability to read and comprehend their world in books, activities, communication and listening. As a student's vocabulary increases so does his/her ability to read and comprehend learning materials, textbooks, and interpretation of the world around him/her.

The Problem Teaching and Learning Vocabulary

Patterns of Difficulty in Vocabulary

Broadly defined, vocabulary is knowledge of words and word meanings. However, vocabulary is more complex than this definition suggests. First, words come in two forms: oral and print. Oral vocabulary includes those words that we recognize and use in listening and speaking. Print vocabulary includes those words that we recognize and use in reading and writing. Second, word knowledge also comes in two forms, receptive and productive. Receptive vocabulary includes words that we recognize when we hear or see them. Productive vocabulary includes words that we use when we speak or write. Receptive vocabulary is typically larger than productive vocabulary, and may include many words to which we assign some meaning, even if we don't know their full definitions and connotations - or ever use them ourselves as we speak and write.

Adding further complexity, in education, the word vocabulary is used with varying meanings. For example, for beginning reading teachers, the word might be synonymous with "sight vocabulary," by which they mean a set of the most common words in English that young students need to be able to recognize quickly as they see them in print. However, for teachers of upper elementary and secondary school students, vocabulary usually means the "hard" words that students encounter in content area textbook and literature selections [3, p.225].

For purposes of this booklet, we define vocabulary as knowledge of words and word meanings in both oral and print language and in productive and receptive forms. More specifically, we use vocabulary to refer to the kind of words that students must know to read increasingly demanding text with comprehension. We begin by looking closely at why developing this kind of vocabulary is important to reading comprehension.

Introduction of the Vocabulary

Teaching vocabulary skills requires vocabulary instruction that is understood in terms of the following:

Reading vocabulary - words are imperative in understanding the context and the content in reading materials from flyers, books to school textbooks.

Verbal/Speaking vocabulary - children from pre-school to secondary school have an accrued vocabulary list of words that are used in generic conversation and more directed communication.

Writing vocabulary - students learn how to start with the basics of writing sentences to the complexity of constructing research papers and reports.

Listening vocabulary - in earlier grades, students are engaged in active listening skills that contribute new words to their vocabulary. As students transition from grade level to grade level, vocabulary words gained from active communication increases or decreases dependent on the student's intention to learn new words and use them and the teacher's ability to facilitate the learning of new worlds

The scientific research on vocabulary instruction reveals that most vocabulary is acquired incidentally through indirect exposure to words. Students can acquire vocabulary incidentally by engaging in rich oral-language experiences at home and at school, listening to books read aloud to them, and reading widely on their own. Reading volume is very important in terms of long-term vocabulary development.

Kamil and Hiebert reason that extensive reading gives students repeated or multiple exposures to words and is also one of the means by which students see vocabulary in rich contexts. Cunningham recommends providing structured read-aloud and discussion sessions

and extending independent reading experiences outside school hours to encourage vocabulary growth in students.

Teaching Vocabulary in English Language: Effective Methodologies

It is noteworthy to mention here that vocabulary items are imparted mostly by translation: either a list of words with their translation at the beginning of the lesson or the translation of the content having new words or glossaries at the very end. This is an erroneous practice as it leads to a state of confusion for the learners. On the teaching skills of vocabulary items, Firstly commented that "While the teacher is not, himself, concerned with the actual selection of vocabulary for text book purposes since practically all the books we use are based on limited vocabularies, it is important that he/she (the teacher) should know the principles, which underlie vocabulary selection" [15, p.34]. Thus it signifies that a language teacher should be innovative and proficient in the application of methodologies pertaining to teaching vocabulary items in a classroom situation.

Following are the main methodologies for teaching vocabulary items in an English language classroom.

Listening Carefully

Careful listening to the words may be a good option in teaching vocabulary items in a heterogenic classroom. "Let the students hear the word in isolation and in a sentence. If the sounds of the word have been mastered, the students will hear it correctly with two or three repetitions. "

Slow pronunciation without distortion will help. Breaking the word into parts and building up to the whole word will also be helpful.

Pronouncing the Word

Pronouncing the word enables the students to remember it longer and identify it more readily when they hear or see it.

Antonyms

When one member of a pair of opposites is understood, the meaning of the other can be easily comprehended. This helps the student to understand the different shades of meanings of a word.

Synonyms

A synonym may be used to help the student to understand the different shades of meaning if the synonym is better known than the word being taught. Synonyms help to enrich a student's vocabulary bank and provide alternative words instantly.

Conclusion

During the given course paper writing we have investigated different matters, related to the problem of teaching vocabulary.

Special attention has been drawn to the problem of the vocabulary introduction and to the effective methodologies of teaching vocabulary in the English language.

We have thoroughly investigated the key strategies of teaching vocabulary and suggested the most efficient ways of determining the vocabulary comprehension and remembering.

Thus, we have come to the following conclusions.

An efficient language teacher can use selected vocabulary activities or can use integrated activities. All this depends upon ability and level of understanding and interest of the learners. There is no sure fire remedy or method to enhance vocabulary in a day or two. A student's

vocabulary bank can be enriched on a gradual basis and one should always show keen interest and enthusiasm in finding, learning and understanding new words.

We have concluded, teaching students vocabulary skills can encompass strategies that use the different types of vocabulary instruction in creating word context, content, meaning and application that will prove beneficial and powerful as the student grows to understand the importance and application of words.

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